

**IMPACT OF SCHOOL-BASED MANAGEMENT LEVEL OF PRACTICES AMONG
SECONDARY SCHOOL IMPLEMENTING UNITS ON THE K TO 12 PROGRAM
IMPLEMENTATION IN LEYTE DIVISION, PHILIPPINES****Hermalin N. Tapayan*, Francisco M. Ebio, Jr. & Claire Theresa S. Bentor**

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to assess the impact of school-based management level of practices among secondary school implementing units on the K to 12 program implementation in Leyte Division, Philippines. It utilized the descriptive-survey method involving 144 school heads as respondents. With respect to K to 12 program implementation, all secondary schools were on the “practicing stage” while most secondary schools were considered to be in the “starting stage” and “gearing up stage.” The impact of school-based management in all the dimensions of: school leadership, school improvement processes, school-based resources and school performance accountability was only moderate. There is a significant relationship between the level of practices of school-based management and the secondary school implementing units on the K to 12 Program implementation. Secondary school heads need to undergo more intensive trainings in order for their schools to be more responsive to the K to 12 program.

KEYWORDS: impact; management; practices; program; implementation.

INTRODUCTION

School-based management (SBM) came into existence to bring about significant change in educational practice and empower school staff to create conditions in schools that facilitate improvement, innovation and continuous professional growth (1987). As a key component of Basic Education Sector Reform Agenda (BESRA), it intended to equip secondary schools to empower its key officials to make “informed and localized decisions based on their unique needs toward improving educational system.”

It focuses on the decentralization of levels and authority to the school level. Responsibility and decision-making over school operations are transferred to principals, teachers, parents, sometimes students and other school community members. The school-level actors have to conform to, or operate within a set of centrally determined policies. Under SBM, professional responsibility replaces bureaucratic regulation.

Meanwhile, the K to 12 basic education program of the Philippines emerged as a response to the need to improve the competitiveness of the country’s graduates as the previous ten-year basic education cycle had been seen as inadequate for work placement and higher education. This had been the plight of overseas Filipino workers who passed the ten-year basic education curriculum, yet they are not automatically recognized as professionals in other countries of the world.

Being new in implementation, school heads are tested with respect to awareness, total understanding and preparedness in the implementation of the program in both human and material resources.

It was along this context that this study was undertaken on the belief that its results would pave the way to empowering secondary school administrators and improve their educational practices, and ultimately help K to 12 students to be more knowledgeable, responsible, socially-skilled, healthy and well-prepared for the world of work.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The following literature is reviewed to provide substance and support to the study.

Malen, Ogawa and Kranz (1990) stressed that in SBM, responsibility for and decision-making authority over school operations are transferred to principals, teachers, parents and sometime to students and other school community members; although these school-level acts have to conform to or operate within a set of policies determined by the central government.

Gamage and Zajda (2005) pointed out strongly that the concept of local community participation and partnership in SBM is a major concern in school reforms where decentralization and delegation of authority occurs at the school level thus empowering the school community to perform most of the functions performed earlier by the central region or the district. Teachers, school administrators, parents and the local community who are the closest to the children are the best-placed people to determine the strategies that meet the needs of their particular students.

Drysdale, Goode and Gurr (2009) cited positive development and outcomes of SBM implementation in the Australian education systems after their departure from a highly-centralized education system established in 1872. In Victoria, since the 1970s, the decentralized system of school governance with an emphasis on a clear shift of operational decision-making authority to the school as well as building partnerships between school, parents and community was effected with strategic policies formulated and applied; and researchers report that Victoria is currently implementing the most devolved system resulting in the improvements of student outcomes and the now well-known Victorian SBM policies have had influence on the teaching –learning environments.

Brouwer, Brekelmans, Nieuwenhuis and Simons (2012) pointed out that the theory behind SBM is that good education involves not only physical input – such as classrooms, teachers and textbooks but also incentives that lead to better instruction and learning. They stressed that the incentives that affect learning outcomes are institutional in nature, categorized into: choice and competition, school autonomy and school accountability.

SBM policies actually changed the dynamics of the school- that the leadership of principals has created supportive teaching and learning environments in schools leading to the enhancement of the quality of education for students (Sanzo, Sherman and Clayton, 2011). This reiterated the findings of Crum and Sherman (2008) which stressed the fact that parents got more involved and/or teachers changed their ways.

Duflo, Dupas and Kremer (2007) also showed strong positive evidence on the impact of SBM in their randomized experiment in Kenya where SBM initiative implemented in randomly selected schools “had large positive effects on student test scores.” These effects were the result of “a combination of smaller class sizes, more teacher incentives and greater parental oversight.” This finding contrasted to the previous finding of de Barros and Mendonca (1998) which declared that “the reform in Brazil had produced no test scores improvement after 11 years of implementation.

Patrinos and Kagia (2007) disclosed that SBM’s decentralized decision-making to parents and communities fosters demand and ensures that the schools provide the social and economic benefits that best reflect the priorities and values of those local communities. With these, school improvement is supposed to be collaborative efforts of all, not only by the school head. It is a shared responsibility.

The foregoing literature provided relevant concepts and information utilized in this study.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The primary purpose of this study was to determine the impact of School-Based Management (SBM) level of practices among the Secondary School Implementing Units (SSIUs) on the K to 12 program implementation in Leyte Division.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following objectives:

1. Ascertain the level of practices among the SSIUs on the K to 12 Program implementation;
2. Find out the impact of SBM level of practices among the SSIUs on the K to 12 Program implementation in terms of the following dimensions:
 - 2.1 school leadership;

- 2.2 school improvement process;
- 2.3 school-based resources and
- 2.4 school performance accountability;
- 3. Find out the significant relationship between the level of practices of SBM and the SSIUs on the K to 12 Program implementation.

Null Hypothesis

As basis whether to negate or confirm the hypothesis, the following null hypothesis was formulated:

H₀₁ There is no significant relationship between the level of practices of SBM and the SSIUs on the K to 12 program implementation.

Framework of the Study

This study was anchored on the following theoretical and conceptual frameworks:

Theoretical framework. The Systems Theory of Von Bertalanffy (1968), which reacts against reductionism and attempts to revive the unity of science, emphasizes that a phenomenon, an entity, or an organization is comprised with real systems and that these “real systems are open to, and interact with, their environments, and that they can acquire qualitatively new properties through emergence, resulting in continual evolution.”

Rather than reducing an entity (e.g. the school) to the properties of its parts or elements (e.g. administrator, teachers, stakeholders), systems theory focuses on the arrangement of and relations between the parts which connect them into a whole.

This particular organization determines a system which is independent of the concrete substance of the elements (e.g. facilities, classrooms, buildings, people, etc.). Thus, the same concepts and principles of organization underlie the different disciplines (e.g. philosophy, psychology, sociology, technology, etc.) providing a basis for their unification.

With respect to the present research, the practices of the SSIUs on the K to 12 program implementation interact with the SBM practices of concerned schools thus leading to educational evolution.

Conceptual framework. This study focused on the impact of SBM level of practices among SSIUs on the K to 12 program implementation. To deeply appraise the objective of the study, it considered the level of practices of SSIUs on the said program and ascertain whether there was a significant relationship between the variables.

Figure 1 presents the conceptual framework of the study.

Figure 1. Conceptual framework of the study

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

The study focused on determining the impact of SBM level of practices among SSIUs on the K to 12 program implementation. Assessment involved only selected autonomous secondary schools in Leyte Division, Philippines, thus limiting the generalizability of the results of this study to a certain school group.

METHODOLOGY

This chapter discusses the methods and processes used in the study. It deals with the descriptions of research design, research locale, research subjects, research instrument, data gathering procedure and statistical treatment of data.

Research Design

This study utilized the descriptive-survey method. Said method was appropriate for the study because the questionnaire was the major tool used in gathering the data and the measurement procedures and analysis of data strictly followed that of survey or descriptive research.

Research Locale

The study covered nine (9) fiscally-autonomous secondary schools in Leyte Division, Philippines, namely: Bato School of Fisheries, Hilongos National High School, Baybay National High School, Dr. Geronimo B. Zaldivar Memorial School of Fisheries, Merida Vocational School, Dulag National High School, Burauen Comprehensive National High School, Carigara National High School and Leyte Agro-Industrial School.

Research Subjects

In this study, there were 144 respondents who comprised the secondary school teachers and school heads from the nine (9) fiscally-autonomous secondary schools in Leyte Division, Philippines.

Table 1 presents the distribution of respondents from the nine (9) fiscally-autonomous secondary schools in Leyte Division, Philippines.

Table Distribution of Respondents

Name of School	F	%
Bato School of Fisheries	11	7.64
Baybay National High School	31	21.53
Burauen Comprehensive National High School	16	11.11
Carigara National High School	16	11.11
Dr. Geronimo B. Zaldivar Memorial School of Fisheries	14	9.72
Dulag National High School	15	10.42
Hilongos National High School	17	11.81
Leyte Agro-Industrial School	12	8.33
Merida Vocational School	12	8.33
Total	144	100.00

Research Instrument

This research made use of a survey questionnaire, standardized assessment tool for School-Based Level of Practices and secondary data from the Department of Education Regional Office No. 8 and Educational Management Information System (EMIS) through the Regional and Division SBM coordinators. Other data were also gathered through semi-structured interviews, focused-group discussion and available documents such as accomplishment reports regularly submitted by the school heads and SBM coordinators.

The survey questionnaire was designed to elicit data on the level of practices of the SSIUs and the extent of impact of the SBM implementation among the implementing units.

The interview focused on the following: Part I elicits information regarding the school heads' awareness and understanding of the K to 12 Basic Education Program, Part II elicits information regarding their way of preparing their school and constituents for the K to 12 Program Implementation, and Part III elicits information regarding the challenges faced by the school heads and their teachers and the difficulties the latter encountered in the implementation of the new curriculum.

Data Gathering Procedure

With due permission, questionnaires were distributed to the school heads and teachers of the respondent schools. Analysis and interpretation of data were done after the retrieval of the questionnaires.

The interviews were done immediately after the questionnaires were retrieved. Data gathered were organized and presented to the school heads and teachers concerned for validation and then came up with a summary.

Data Scoring

To determine the level of practices of SSIUs on the K to 12 Program implementation, the following rating scale, which was stipulated by the SBM Practices Assessment Manual, was used:

<i>Level</i>	<i>Raw Score (%)</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1	100%	Standard Stage
	61-99%	"Moving Toward" Stage
	1-60%	Starting Stage
2	100%	Progressive Stage
	61-99%	Advancing Stage
	1-60%	Gearing Up Stage
3	100%	Mature Stage
	61-99%	Accelerating Stage
	1-60%	Practicing Stage

To interpret the impact of SBM practices among secondary schools, the following rating scale was used:

<i>Raw Score (AWM)</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
4.6 and above	Very Strong Impact
3.6 – 4.5	Strong Impact
2.6 – 3.5	Moderate Impact
1.6 – 2.5	Weak Impact
1.5 and below	Very Weak or No Impact

Statistical Treatment of Data

The study utilized descriptive statistics like percentage to determine the level of practices of the SSIUs on the K to 12 program implementation while the mean was used to determine the impact of SBM practices among the secondary schools.

The Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation, also called Pearson r , was used to determine the significant relationship between the level of practices of the SSIUs on the K to 12 program implementation and the impact of SBM level of practices.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter presents the results and discussion of the data based on the objectives of the study. It includes the level of practices of SSIUs on the K to 12 Program implementation, the impact of SBM level of practices among secondary schools and the significant relationship between the level of practices of SSIUs and the impact of SBM level of practices among secondary schools.

Level of Practices of SSIUs on the K to 12 Program Implementation

The level of practices was categorized into: level 1, level 2 and level 3. This is presented in Table 2.

Table 2
Level of Practices of SSIUs on the K to 12 Program Implementation

School Code	Level of Practices	Average Rating (%)	Interpretation
A	Level 1	14	Starting Stage
	Level 2	78	Advancing Stage
	Level 3	6	Practicing Stage
B	Level 1	6	Starting Stage
	Level 2	58	Gearing Up Stage
	Level 3	39	Practicing Stage
C	Level 1	6	Starting Stage
	Level 2	42	Gearing Up Stage
	Level 3	56	Practicing Stage
D	Level 1	94	“Moving Toward” Stage
	Level 2	6	Gearing Up Stage
	Level 3	6	Practicing Stage
E	Level 1	39	Starting Stage
	Level 2	58	Gearing Up Stage
	Level 3	3	Practicing Stage
F	Level 1	75	“Moving Toward” Stage
	Level 2	25	Gearing Up Stage
	Level 3	3	Practicing Stage
G	Level 1	83	“Moving Toward” Stage
	Level 2	14	Gearing Up Stage
	Level 3	3	Practicing Stage
H	Level 1	89	“Moving Toward” Stage
	Level 2	14	Gearing Up Stage
	Level 3	3	Practicing Stage
I	Level 1	3	Starting Stage
	Level 2	42	Gearing Up Stage
	Level 3	58	Practicing Stage
Overall Rating	Level 1	45.44	Starting Stage
	Level 2	37.44	Gearing Up Stage
	Level 3	19.66	Practicing Stage

As shown in Table 2, each level of practices has three stages. For level 1, the school is in the “standard stage” when it has a rating of 100 per cent. It is in the “moving toward stage” when the school has a rating of 61-99 per cent and in the “starting stage” when it has a rating of 1-60 per cent.

The overall rating of 45.44 per cent in level 1 practices of SSIUs on the K to 12 Program implementation revealed that said level is in the “starting stage”. Data imply that much more are still needed by the secondary schools in the implementation of the K to 12 Program like facilities, equipment, instructional materials, adequately-trained teachers and the like.

For level 2, the school is in the “progressive stage” when it has a rating of 100 per cent, “advancing stage” when it has a rating of 61-99 per cent and in the “gearing up stage” when it has a rating of 1-60 per cent.

The overall rating of 37.44 per cent in level 2 practices of SSIUs on the K to 12 Program implementation revealed that said level is in the “gearing up stage”. This would imply that the secondary schools need to intensify all its resources and maximize efforts in order to achieve desired learning outcomes which are responsive to K to 12 Program.

For level 3, the school is in the “mature stage” when it has a rating of 100 per cent, “accelerating stage” when it has a rating of 61-99 per cent and in the “practicing stage” when it has a rating of 1-60 per cent.

The overall rating of 19.66 per cent in level 3 practices of SSIUs on the K to 12 Program implementation showed that said level is in the “practicing stage”. This would imply that the secondary schools need to constantly implement and even improve what they have started in order to achieve optimum learning outcomes.

Impact of the School-Based Management Level of Practices

The impact of SBM level of practices included the following dimensions: *school leadership*, *school improvement*, *school-based resources* and *school performance accountability*. Table 3 presents the impact of the SBM level of practices among SSIUs in *school leadership* dimension.

Table 3 Impact of the SBM Level of Practices among SSIUs in School Leadership Dimension

Indicators	AWM	Interpretation
Documents showing attendance in induction and/or orientation on basic leadership and management roles of the school head	3.07	Moderate Impact
School annual plan document	3.08	Moderate Impact
Has attended SBM-related trainings		
Basic SBM	3.08	Moderate Impact
School Improvement Plan/Annual Improvement Plan	3.07	Moderate Impact
Annual School Budget	2.91	Moderate Impact
Fiscal Management	2.91	Moderate Impact
ICT Training	3.08	Moderate Impact
Documents showing roles and responsibilities of each organized Internal/external stakeholder group		
List of officials of internal stakeholders:		
Student organization	3.00	Moderate Impact
Parent organization	3.08	Moderate Impact
Teacher organization	3.07	Moderate Impact
List of officials of external stakeholders		
Local government unit/organization	3.00	Moderate Impact
Record of meetings/orientation on roles and responsibilities of each internal/external stakeholder group	3.03	Moderate Impact
Organized teams and list of membership per team		
Management Information System	3.00	Moderate Impact
School Improvement Plan-School Planning Team	3.00	Moderate Impact
In-Service Training Mechanism	3.08	Moderate Impact
Monitoring and Evaluation Mechanism	3.00	Moderate Impact
Financial Management System	3.04	Moderate Impact
School Staffing System	3.06	Moderate Impact
Records of orientation on SBM systems and organizational set up of school teams	3.08	Moderate Impact
Records of resource generation from different sources		
Maintenance and other operating expenses	2.91	Moderate Impact
Local school board/special education fund	3.08	Moderate Impact
Adopt-a-school	2.91	Moderate Impact
Donations	3.07	Moderate Impact
Income generating projects	2.91	Moderate Impact
Parents-teachers-community association support	3.08	Moderate Impact

Overall Mean	3.02	Moderate Impact
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School leadership dimension. Data on Table 3 showed that all indicators on the impact of the SBM level of practices among the SSIUs in *school leadership* dimension were all perceived “moderate impact”. The overall mean of 3.02 revealed that the impact of SBM level of practices among the SSIUs in *school leadership* dimension was only “moderate”. This would imply that school management is not the vital factor to be considered when it comes to school overall performance.

School improvement process dimension. Table 4 presents the impact of the SBM level of practices among the SSIUs in *school improvement process* dimension.

Table 4 Impact of the SBM Level of Practices among SSIUs in School Improvement Process Dimension

Indicators	AWM	Interpretation
Self-assessment guide of SBM practices accomplished	3.04	Moderate Impact
SBM assessment results analysed	3.06	Moderate Impact
Data on school performance indicator gathered	2.92	Moderate Impact
school data against national standard analysed	3.04	Moderate Impact
Records on the trend analysis of results on the assessment of SBM practices submitted to the Division for provision of technical assistance	2.92	Moderate Impact
School governing council is organized	2.95	Moderate Impact
List of officers with roles and responsibilities provided	3.07	Moderate Impact
Constitution and by-laws provided	2.91	Moderate Impact
Operating procedures followed	2.91	Moderate Impact
Documents/records showing school planning team leading the development of the school improvement plan/annual improvement plan	2.93	Moderate Impact
Stakeholders involved in the school improvement plan/annual improvement plan implementation	2.95	Moderate Impact
School improvement plan/annual improvement plan attained the goals relevant to school performance indicators	3.13	Moderate Impact
Overall Mean	2.99	Moderate Impact

Data on Table 4 showed that all indicators on the impact of the SBM level of practices among the SSIUs in *school improvement process* dimension were all perceived “moderate impact”. The overall mean of 2.99 revealed that the impact of SBM level of practices among the SSIUs in *school improvement process* dimension was only “moderate”. This would imply that school management does not necessarily influence the school’s procedures and standards in achieving educational improvement.

School-based resources dimension. Table 5 presents the impact of SBM level of practices among the SSIUs in *school-based resources* dimension.

Table 5 Impact of SBM Level of Practices among the SSIUs in School-Based Resources Dimension

Indicators	AWM	Interpretation
Annual School Budget (ASB) submitted and reviewed by the Division Office	3.00	Moderate Impact
ASB reflecting Maintenance and Other Operating Expenses (MOOE) and other sources of funding for Annual Improvement Plan (AIP) programs/projects	2.92	Moderate Impact
Procurement Plan aligned with ASB	2.93	Moderate Impact

Records of representation/advocacy for Local School Board (LSB) support to AIP made by Department of Education (DepED) representative	2.96	Moderate Impact
ASB supported interventions/programs/projects, attained school targets on:		
Enrollment	3.00	Moderate Impact
Drop Out Rate	2.26	Moderate Impact
Retention Rate	3.00	Moderate Impact
Completion Rate	3.00	Moderate Impact
Achievement Rate	3.08	Moderate Impact
Recorded utilization of downloaded school MOOE with assistance from Division Office	2.92	Moderate Impact
Division Office granted school head minimal signing authority on financial transactions	2.92	Moderate Impact
School management designated fiscal staff	3.00	Moderate Impact
Designated fiscal staff trained on bookkeeping and disbursement	2.99	Moderate Impact
Records of needs analysis undertaken	2.92	Moderate Impact
Records in accounting/auditing of funds submitted	3.08	Moderate Impact
Annual Procurement Plan submitted	2.95	Moderate Impact
Overall Mean	2.93	Moderate Impact

Data on Table 5 showed that all indicators on the impact of SBM level of practices among the SSIUs in *school-based resources* dimension were all perceived “moderate impact”. The overall mean of 2.93 revealed that the impact of SBM level of practices among the SSIUs in *school-based resources* dimension was only “moderate”. This would imply that school management does not necessarily influence the school’s generation of resources for the improvement of educational outcomes.

School performance accountability dimension. Table 6 presents the impact of SBM level of practices among the SSIUs in *school performance accountability* dimension.

Table 6 Impact of SBM Level of Practices among the SSIUs in School Performance Accountability Dimension

Indicators	AWM	Interpretation
Documents showing monitoring and evaluation tools on:		
Implementation of SIP/AIP	3.00	Moderate Impact
Tracking of student performance	2.98	Moderate Impact
Tracking of teacher performance	2.95	Moderate Impact
School Governing Council (SGC) operations	2.99	Moderate Impact
Fund management	2.92	Moderate Impact
Guidelines provided on:		
Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E)	3.05	Moderate Impact
Transparency and accountability	2.92	Moderate Impact
M&E reporting system	2.98	Moderate Impact
Committee organized involving internal and external stakeholders in M&E	3.01	Moderate Impact
Reports provided on briefing/orientation on transparency and accountability	2.93	Moderate Impact
School informed and involved major stakeholders in the M&E	3.00	Moderate Impact
Records of reports and information provided to the		
Superintendent	3.00	Moderate Impact
LSB	2.92	Moderate Impact
PTCA	3.08	Moderate Impact

SGC	2.98	Moderate Impact
Records provided on the involvement of the:		
Division Office	2.92	Moderate Impact
LSB	2.93	Moderate Impact
PTCA	3.00	Moderate Impact
SGC	2.96	Moderate Impact
Documents of targets on school performance indicators (enrolment, retention rate, completion rate, cohort survival rate and student achievement) are disseminated to internal and external stakeholders	3.00	Moderate Impact
Overall Mean	2.98	Moderate Impact

Data on Table 6 showed that all indicators on the impact of SBM level of practices among the SSIUs in *school performance accountability* dimension were all perceived “moderate impact”. The overall mean of 2.98 revealed that the impact of SBM level of practices among the SSIUs in *school performance accountability* dimension was only “moderate”. This would imply that the school’s responsibility, obligation and accountability with respect to educational achievement are not strongly influenced by school management.

Summary of the Impact of SBM Level of Practices among the SSIUs in the Different Dimensions. Table 7 presents the summary of the dimensions on the impact of SBM level of practices among the SSIUs.

Table 7 Summary of the Impact of SBM Level of Practices among the SSIUs in the Different Dimensions

Dimension	AWM	Interpretation
School Leadership	3.02	Moderate Impact
School Improvement Process	2.99	Moderate Impact
School-Based Resources	2.93	Moderate Impact
School Performance Accountability	2.98	Moderate Impact
Overall Mean	2.98	Moderate Impact

Data on Table 7 showed that all dimensions on the impact of SBM level of practices among the SSIUs were all perceived “moderate impact”. This would imply that the school’s procedures and standards; generation of resources; responsibilities, obligations and accountabilities necessary for overall educational performance are not necessarily influenced by school management.

Relationship Between the Level of Practices of SBM and the SSIUs on the K to 12 Program Implementation. Table 8 presents the relationship between the level of practices of SBM and the SSIUs on the K to 12 program implementation.

Table 8 Relationship Between the Level of Practices of SBM and the SSIUs on the K to 12 Program Implementation

Variables	r	Cv	tv	Interpretation
Level of practices of SBM and the SSIUs on the K to 12 program implementation	0.83	2.98	2.132	Significant

Alpha level of significance = .05

df = 4

Data on Table 8 showed that the computed t-value of 2.98 was greater than the table value of 2.132. The null hypothesis that there was no significant relationship between the level of practices of SBM and the SSIUs on the K to 12 program implementation was rejected, thus there was a significant relationship between the said variables. This would imply that the higher is the level of school management, the higher would also be the level of SSIUs with respect to K to 12 program implementation.

CONCLUSIONS

The level of practices among SSIUs on the K to 12 program implementation were varied. Most schools for level 1 (standard level) were in the “starting stage”, for level 2 (progressive level), majority were in the “gearing up stage”, and for level 3 (mature level), all were in the “practicing stage”.

The impact of SBM level of practices among the SSIUs on the K to 12 program implementation in the dimensions of: *school leadership, school improvement process, school-based resources and school performance accountability* was only “moderate”.

There was a significant relationship between the level of practices of SBM and the SSIUs on the K to 12 program implementation.

RECOMENDATIONS

Secondary school heads need to undergo more intensive trainings in order for the schools to be more responsive to the K to 12 program.

Authorities may strictly and firmly consider education, training, experience and outstanding accomplishments as essential requirements for evaluation and selection of individuals who will lead or participate in implementing school change.

A study may be replicated to determine whether the level of practices among SSIUs has intensified to the benefit of the attainment of the new program’s objectives and find out areas of strengths vis-à-vis areas of weaknesses to ascertain upgraded strategies for advanced implementation of the K to 12 program.

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Appendix A
SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE

Dear Respondent,

Greetings of Peace!

Please feel free to answer this questionnaire. It is highly requested that answers to be reflected must be from the best of your knowledge in order to arrive at valid results. Your cooperation is appreciated and rest assured all your responses would be kept confidential.

Thank you and more power.

Respectfully,
The Researcher

I. School Basic Information

Name of School: _____

Division: _____

Position of School Head: _____

Number of Years of the School Head in the Present School: _____

Number of Years of SBM Implementation: _____

II. Level of Practices among SSIUs on K to 12 Program Implementation

(Kindly put a check (/) mark inside the parenthesis.)

Dimension	Level 3 (Mature)	Level 2 (Progressive)	Level 1 (Standard)
School Leadership	() School head is fully accountable to stakeholders for school performance	() School head performs greater responsibility and accountability in school management	() School head is designated
	() School head significantly influences student learning outcomes	() School head exercises instructional leadership and management functions; pursues continuing professional development	() School head is trained on basic competencies on instructional leadership
	() School head promotes, shares SBM experiences and leading practices to other schools; creates critical mass of SBM champions	() School head has a resource on SBM (e.g., acts as mentor/coach)	() School head is trained on SBM and LSB responsibilities
	() School head has effective working relationship with LSB and SGC; involves and institutionalizes continuous school improvement process	() School head cooperates with organized stakeholders; manages SBM system	() School head initiates: organizing stakeholders, installing appropriate SBM system (e.g., school improvement planning, budgeting and resource management, staffing, performance monitoring and reporting)
	() School head acts as fund manager and	() School head relieved of	() School head performs fund management duties

	devotes more attention to instructional leadership and supervision	accounting/bookkeeping functions and devotes more attention to instructional leadership and supervision	(e.g., accounting/bookkeeping functions
School Improvement Process	<input type="checkbox"/> Institutionalized assessment of SBM practice using assessment tool; SGC demands champions and continuous school improvement process	<input type="checkbox"/> Periodic assessment of SBM practice using assessment tool; SGC supports continuous school improvement process	<input type="checkbox"/> School conducts assessment of SBM practice using assessment tool; SGC is organized
	<input type="checkbox"/> SGC members are held accountable for school performance	<input type="checkbox"/> SGC members are performing their respective duties and responsibilities	<input type="checkbox"/> SGC members are oriented and trained on SBM and school governance; they are made aware of their duties and responsibilities
	<input type="checkbox"/> SIP, AIP surpasses national, regional, division performance standards; national, regional and division plans and programs are based on SIPs and AIPs	<input type="checkbox"/> Stakeholders are informed, consulted and engaged in SIP, AIP formulation, implementation, monitoring, evaluation and are satisfied with school performance	<input type="checkbox"/> SIP, AIP implementation is regularly tracked and reported with necessary corrective measures undertaken
	<input type="checkbox"/> Best practices are institutionalized	<input type="checkbox"/> Best practices are replicated	<input type="checkbox"/> Best practices are identified, documented and shared among peers
	<input type="checkbox"/> Resources and funds are sustained by LGU and community partners through supplemental budget community equity	<input type="checkbox"/> Resources and funds are augmented with LSB and community contributions and allocated to meet desired educational outcomes	<input type="checkbox"/> Resources and funds (MOOE) are linked to SIP/AIP targets and allocated to meet minimum educational cost requirements (e.g., student per capita)
	<input type="checkbox"/> A system of incentives and rewards is institutionalized with DepEd and stakeholder support to sustain school improvement process	<input type="checkbox"/> A system of incentives and rewards is established with DepEd and stakeholder support to sustain school improvement process	<input type="checkbox"/> A system of incentives and rewards is piloted to promote school improvement process
	<input type="checkbox"/> A system of technical assistance is optimized for continuous school improvement process and learners' well-being	<input type="checkbox"/> A system of technical assistance is strengthened for continuous school improvement process	<input type="checkbox"/> A system of technical assistance is installed for continuous school improvement process
	School-Based Resources	<input type="checkbox"/> ASB (DepEd MOOE + SEF + community contribution and LGU supplemental budget + grants/loans) is aligned with SIP/AIP	<input type="checkbox"/> ASB (DepEd MOOE + SEF + community contributions) is aligned with SIP/AIP

	() School fully manages and controls funds/resources	() School manages and controls funds/resources with Division Office technical guidance	() School fully manages and controls funds/resources with Division Office assistance
	() ASB is executed with best practices and innovations resulting in improved school performance	() ASB is executed with efficiency and cost effectiveness	() ASB is executed in accordance with guidelines
	() ASB results in sustained excellent performance	() ASB results in surpassed targets and desired outcomes	() ASB results in attainment of targets and desired outcomes
	() School budget is sustained and institutionalized by LGU and community partners through supplemental budget and community equity	() School MOOE allocation is augmented with LSB and community contributions to meet desired educational outcomes	() School is properly informed of MOOE allocation/MOOE is published and drilled down to schools in cash
	() School undertakes own school-based procurement including IMTEX, furniture and equipment, SBP subject to DepEd wide guidelines	() School undertakes school-based procurement with Division Office guidance	() School undertakes school-based procurement with Division Office assistance
	() DepEd representatives to the LSB monitor and influence SEF for sustained support to SIP/AIP	() DepEd representatives to the LSB ensure that SEF budget priorities support SIP/AIP and reflect increased number of educational resources	() DepEd representatives to the LSB are knowledgeable of SIP priorities
	() All resources and funds made available to the school are recorded, optimally utilized, reported and accounted for	() Some resources and funds made available to the school are recorded, optimally utilized, reported and accounted for	() MOOE funds made available to the school are recorded, optimally utilized, reported and accounted for.
School Performance Accountability	() School is fully transparent and accountable	() School exercises transparency and accountability in carrying out its functions	() School introduces transparency and accountability mechanisms
	() Stakeholders and school jointly develop and implement multi-sectoral and multi-dimensional M/E system with innovations	() Performance and results-based M/E system is fully operational and utilized in planning	() M/E system is installed and operational
	() Stakeholders hold themselves accountable for school performance	() All stakeholders fully participate in M/E and reporting activities	() Major stakeholders are informed and participate in M/E and reporting

	() School performance is presented, published and validated through community satisfaction surveys	() Quarterly and annual school performance are monitored and evaluated by community stakeholders	() Quarterly school performance is monitored and evaluated by community stakeholders
	() Improvements in learning outcomes are tracked for benchmarking with other SBM schools	() Improvement in learning outcomes is monitored and evaluated on school-wide basis	() Improvement in learning outcomes is monitored and evaluated by homeroom and tracked per student/subject

III. Impact of SBM Level of Practices on K to 12 Program Implementation

(Kindly put a check (/) mark on the space/box provided that corresponds your choice using the rating scale as follows:

- 5 - Very large impact
- 4 - Large impact
- 3 - Moderate impact
- 2 - Slight impact
- 1 - No impact

Impact of the SBM Level of Practices among SSIUs in School Leadership Dimension

Indicators	5	4	3	2	1
Documents showing attendance in induction and/or orientation on basic leadership and management roles of the school head					
School annual plan document					
Has attended SBM-related trainings					
Basic SBM					
School Improvement Plan/Annual Improvement Plan					
Annual School Budget					
Fiscal Management					
ICT Training					
Documents showing roles and responsibilities of each organized Internal/external stakeholder group					
List of officials of internal stakeholders:					
Student organization					
Parent organization					
Teacher organization					
List of officials of external stakeholders					
Local government unit/organization					
Record of meetings/orientation on roles and responsibilities of each internal/external stakeholder group					
Organized teams and list of membership per team					
Management Information System					
School Improvement Plan-School Planning Team					
In-Service Training Mechanism					
Monitoring and Evaluation Mechanism					
Financial Management System					
School Staffing System					

Records of orientation on SBM systems and organizational set up of school teams					
Records of resource generation from different sources Maintenance and other operating expenses Local school board/special education fund Adopt-a-school Donations Income generating projects Parents-teachers-community association support					

Impact of the SBM Level of Practices among SSIUs in School Improvement Process Dimension

Indicators	5	4	3	2	1
Self-assessment guide of SBM practices accomplished					
SBM assessment results analysed					
Data on school performance indicator gathered					
school data against national standard analysed					
Records on the trend analysis of results on the assessment of SBM practices submitted to the Division for provision of technical assistance					
School governing council is organized					
List of officers with roles and responsibilities provided					
Constitution and by-laws provided					
Operating procedures followed					
Documents/records showing school planning team leading the development of the school improvement plan/annual improvement plan					
Stakeholders involved in the school improvement plan/annual improvement plan implementation					
School improvement plan/annual improvement plan attained the goals relevant to school performance indicators					

Impact of SBM Level of Practices among the SSIUs in School-Based Resources Dimension

Indicators	5	4	3	2	1
Annual School Budget (ASB) submitted and reviewed by the Division Office					
ASB reflecting Maintenance and Other Operating Expenses (MOOE) and other sources of funding for Annual Improvement Plan (AIP) programs/projects					
Procurement Plan aligned with ASB					
Records of representation/advocacy for Local School Board (LSB) support to AIP made by Department of Education (DepED) representative					
ASB supported interventions/programs/projects, attained school targets on:					
Enrollment					
Drop Out Rate					
Retention Rate					
Completion Rate					
Achievement Rate					
Recorded utilization of downloaded school MOOE with assistance from Division Office					
Division Office granted school head minimal signing authority on financial transactions					
School management designated fiscal staff					
Designated fiscal staff trained on bookkeeping and disbursement					
Records of needs analysis undertaken					
Records in accounting/auditing of funds submitted					

Annual Procurement Plan submitted					
Impact of SBM Level of Practices among the SSIUs in <i>School Performance Accountability</i> Dimension					
Indicators	5	4	3	2	1
Documents showing monitoring and evaluation tools on: Implementation of SIP/AIP Tracking of student performance Tracking of teacher performance School Governing Council (SGC) operations Fund management					
Guidelines provided on: Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E) Transparency and accountability M&E reporting system					
Committee organized involving internal and external stakeholders in M&E					
Reports provided on briefing/orientation on transparency and accountability					
School informed and involved major stakeholders in the M&E					
Records of reports and information provided to the Superintendent LSB PTCA SGC					
Records provided on the involvement of the: Division Office LSB PTCA SGC					
Documents of targets on school performance indicators (enrolment, retention rate, completion rate, cohort survival rate and student achievement) are disseminated to internal and external stakeholders					